

Mathematical standardisation on random chain model : Gaussian to computational approach

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Abstract : Random Chain model is mathematically standardised using Taylor's expansion series, second order partial differential equation and Laplace transformation in details to establish the most important physical properties like probability distribution function and mean square separation of end to end of a biopolymer chain. A multivariable function correlating mean end to end separation, number of monomer unit and length of each monomer unit is established. Finally the output equations are standardised by an object oriented programming language like C++ for biopolymers like Catalase, Myosin and Bushy shunt virus.

Keywords : Mean square separation of end to end, Random Chain, Taylor's expansion series, second order partial differential equation, Laplace transformation, Catalase, Myosin, Bushy shunt virus, rotational isomer model.

Introduction

Random Coil model has been analysed¹ by Stirling's approximation, Gamma function and Weight factor in details in continuation of earlier work² by Torre and Carrasco. The output equations were validated for a standard protein biomolecule like Serum Albumin. The present work shows the mathematical standardisation of two most important physical properties like probability distribution function and mean square separation of end to end of a biopolymer chain using Taylor's expansion series, second order partial differential equation and Laplace transformation in details. The equations obtained as a result of mathematical standardisation are validated by a standard object oriented programming language like C++ for biomolecules like Catalase, Myosin and Bushy shunt virus.

Results and discussion

The mean square end to end distance³ is only one of many properties of a flexible biopolymer. A more complete description requires knowledge of the probability

distribution³ of the end to end distance, $P(R)$. In an ideal chain the effective segments are uncorrelated, and this information is sufficient to permit the use of a very powerful general result from probability called central limit theorem. This theorem states that any sum of independent random quantities with the same mean will be distributed as Gaussian function. To see how the Gaussian distribution arises in polymers, we start with a simplified model of a random chain in one dimension. Each segment can point in only two directions, right or left. If we see that a chain of N -segments ends at point x , then we know that the chain of $(N-1)$ segments leading up to this point must have terminated at either $(x + \ell)$ or $(x - \ell)$ where ℓ is the length of each segment. We can therefore relate the probability $P(x)$ to the two probabilities $P_{N-1}(x - \ell)$ and $P_{N-1}(x + \ell)$ as follows,

$$P_N(x) = \frac{1}{2} [P_{N-1}(x - \ell) + P_{N-1}(x + \ell)]$$

where the factor ($\frac{1}{2}$) appears because for either of the two possible locations of segments $(N-1)$, the next step

can be either toward or away from x . Expanding each of the terms on the right as Taylor series around x gives,

$$P_N(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[P_{N-1}(x) - \ell \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \frac{\ell^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} + P_{N-1}(x) + \ell \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \frac{\ell^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \right] = P_{N-1}(x) + \frac{\ell^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

since $[P_N(x) - P_{N-1}(x)] = \Delta P$ and $\Delta N = N - (N-1) = 1$, so eq. (1) can be approximated as derivative leading to a second order partial differential equation⁴ in P ,

$$\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial N} \right) = \frac{\ell^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \right) \text{ [where } P(x, N) \text{ is constant]} \quad (2)$$

The results of the value obtained from $\frac{\ell^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \right)$ are

exactly same as the value obtained from $\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial N} \right)$, which could be derived as follows :

Let another trial solution becomes,

$$P = \frac{A'}{\sqrt{N}} \exp \left(-\frac{B'}{N} \right) \text{ [where } P(x, N), x \text{ is constant]}$$

$$\text{and } A' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\ell^2}} \text{ and } B' = \frac{x^2}{2\ell}$$

By applying partial differential on $P(x, N)$ w.r.to N we get

$$\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial N} \right) = \left\{ \frac{\exp \left(-\frac{x^2}{2N\ell^2} \right)}{\sqrt{2\pi N^3 \ell^2}} \right\} \left(\frac{x^2}{2N^2} - 1 \right)$$

\therefore The exact solution of partial differential equation we get,

$$P(x, N) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi N \ell^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{x^2}{2N\ell^2} \right)$$

$$\therefore P_N(x) dx = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi N \ell^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{x^2}{2N\ell^2} \right) dx$$

This is a result for an arbitrary one-dimensional random chain. A more realistic three-dimensional chain is a simple extension. The probability of finding the end of the chain at a coordinate (x, y, z) is taken as the product of the solution of second order partial differential^{4,5} eq. (2), which predicts that the probability is a Gaussian function and can be solved as follows.

Let the trial solution of eq. (2) be the, $P = A \exp(-Bx^2)$ [where $P(x, N)$, N is constant] and $A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi N \ell^2}}$

$$\text{and } B = \frac{1}{2N\ell^2}$$

By applying partial differential in second order with respect to x on the probability $P(x, N)$ we get,

$$\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} = (-2AB)(1 - 2Bx^2) \{ \exp(-Bx^2) \}$$

By putting the values of A and B we get,

$$\frac{\ell^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \right) = \left\{ \frac{\exp \left(-\frac{x^2}{2N\ell^2} \right)}{\sqrt{2\pi N^3 \ell^2}} \right\} \left(\frac{x^2}{N\ell^2} - 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

Here three Gaussians of the form as follows :

$$P_N(x, y, z) dx dy dz = \frac{1}{\left(\sqrt{2\pi N \ell^2} \right)^3}$$

$$\left[\exp \left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}{2N\ell^2} \right) \right] dx dy dz \quad (4)$$

By transferring the above equation from Cartesian to spherical coordinates, where the probability function $P_N(R)$ ⁶ becomes,

$$P_N(R) = 4\pi \left(\frac{3}{2\pi N \ell^2} \right)^{3/2} R^2 \exp \left(-\frac{3R^2}{2N\ell^2} \right) \quad (5)$$

The function $P_N(R)$ can be used to calculate the probability of the ends of a three dimensional freely linked chain in the range R to $R + dR$. We write this probability as $P_N(R) dR$. We know that the mean value $\langle x \rangle$ of a quantity x with values ranging from $x = a$ to $x = b$ is given by

$$\langle x \rangle = \int_a^b x f(x) dx$$

where the function $f(x)$ is the probability density, a measure of the distribution of the probability values, x , and dx is an infinitesimally small interval of x values. The mean value of a function $g(x)$ can be calculated with a similar formula

$$\langle g(x) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} g(x) f(x) dx$$

These concepts are applied to calculate to the mean square separation of the ends of a random coil, which we identify as $P_N(R) dR$ as the probability of the ends of the chain lie in the range $R = r$ to $R = r + dr$, with $P_N(r)$ as the probability density. It follows that the general expression for the mean square of the end-to-end separation (a positive quantity that can vary from 0 to $+\infty$) is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle R^2 \rangle &= 4\pi \left(\frac{3}{2\pi N\ell^2} \right)^{3/2} \int_0^\infty r^4 \exp \left(-\frac{3r^2}{2N\ell^2} \right) \\ &= 4\pi \left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right)^3 \int_0^\infty r^4 \exp(-a^2 r^2) \end{aligned} \quad (6)_{6,7}$$

where $a = \left(\frac{3}{2N\ell^2} \right)^{1/2}$

$\int_0^\infty r^4 \exp(-a^2 r^2) dr$ is a standard integral in the form,

$$\int_0^\infty x^4 e^{-a^2 x^2} dx$$

The above standard integral can be solved by using Laplace transformation as follows.

Let $f(t)$ is a function of t defined for all positive values of t . Then the Laplace transforms⁴ of $f(t)$, denoted by $L\{f(t)\}$ is defined as,

$$L\{f(t)\} = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} f(t) dt$$

s is a parameter which may be a real or a complex number.

$L\{f(t)\}$ being clearly a function of S is briefly written as $\bar{f}(s)$,

i.e. $L\{f(t)\} = \bar{f}(s)$ which can be also written as,
 $f(t) = L^{-1}\{\bar{f}(s)\}$

Then $f(t)$ is called the inverse Laplace transform of $\bar{f}(s)$. The symbol L , which transforms $f(t)$ into $\bar{f}(s)$, is called the Laplace transformation operator.

Transformation of elementary functions,

$$(1) \quad L(1) = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} \cdot 1 \cdot dt = \left| -\frac{e^{-st}}{s} \right|_0^\infty = \frac{1}{s}, \text{ if } s > 0$$

$$(2) \quad L(t^n) = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} \cdot t^n dt = \int_0^\infty e^{-p} \left(\frac{p}{s} \right)^n \frac{dp}{s},$$

on putting $st=p$

From the relationship between Laplace transformation and Gamma function, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^\infty e^{-st} \cdot t^n dt &= \int_0^\infty e^{-p} \left(\frac{p}{s} \right)^n \frac{dp}{s} = \frac{1}{s^{n+1}} \int_0^\infty e^{-p} \cdot p^n dp \\ &= \Gamma(n+1) / s^{n+1}, \text{ if } n > -1 \text{ and } s > 0 \end{aligned}$$

If n be a positive integer, $\Gamma(n+1) = n!$

$$\therefore L(t^n) = \frac{n!}{s^{n+1}}$$

$$\therefore \int_0^\infty x^4 \exp(-a^2 x^2) dx = \frac{1}{2a^5} \int_0^\infty z^{3/2} e^{-z} dz$$

[By applying the method of substitution $a^2 x^2 = z$]

Now by definition,

$$L(z^{3/2}) = \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2} + 1\right) = \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\left(\sqrt{\pi}\right)\left(\frac{3}{4}\right)\sqrt{\pi}$$

[since $s = 1$]

The eq. (6) becomes,

$$\langle R^2 \rangle = \frac{2\pi}{a^5} \left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right)^3 \int_0^\infty z^{3/2} e^{-z} dz$$

$$\langle R^2 \rangle = \frac{3}{2a^2}$$

$$\left[\text{since } L(z^{3/2}) = \frac{3}{4} \sqrt{\pi} \text{ and } a = \left(\frac{3}{2N\ell^2} \right)^{1/2} \right]$$

Putting the values of a we get the function $\langle R^2 \rangle (N, \ell)$

$$\langle R^2 \rangle = N\ell^2 \quad (7)$$

The eq. (7) is a multivariable function of mean square end to end separation, number of monomer units and length of each monomer unit of a biopolymer chain of random coil. A real polymer⁸ is not freely linked. A C-C sigma bond has a fixed angle of 109.5° for α -C atom (C_α). Because of zigzag backbone of a random coil each successive individual bond is constrained to a single cone of angle θ relative to its neighbour, the resultant of several lies in a random direction.

In a chain of N segments, we can define the vector from the beginning of the first segment to the end of the N -th segment.

So $\langle R^2 \rangle$ can be expressed as dot product³ of two segment vectors r_n and r_{n+1} as

$$r_n \cdot r_{n+1} = \ell^2 \cos \theta \text{ as ,}$$

$$\langle R^2 \rangle = [(1 + \cos \theta)/(1 - \cos \theta)] \ell^2 N \quad (8)$$

For tetrahedral bond, $\theta = 109.5^\circ$

$$\langle R^2 \rangle = 0.5 (\ell^2 N) \quad (9)$$

For rotational isomeric model^{3,9} (RIM) the eq. (8) may be modified in the following form,

$$\langle R^2 \rangle = 0.5 [(1 + \cos \Phi)/(1 - \cos \Phi)] \ell^2 N \quad (10)$$

The angle Φ is called dihedral or torsional angle and gives the polymer three dimensional character. The rotational isomer model is very much like stringing the monomers along the points of a lattice. If the bonds are constrained to 90° or multiples of 90°, then a cubic lattice could be assumed.

The value of $\langle R^2 \rangle$ is related to the another most important physical parameters like radius of gyration (R_g) by the following expression^{6,7}.

$$\langle R^2 \rangle = 3R_g^2 \quad (11)$$

The radius of gyration can be also calculated for other geometries¹⁰. For example, a solid uniform sphere of radius R is expressed as,

$$R = 0.527 \langle R^2 \rangle^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

and a long thin uniform rod of length L can be expressed as¹⁰

$$L = 0.471 \langle R^2 \rangle^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

for rotation about an axis perpendicular to the long axis.

So with a known value of radius of gyration (R_g) the value of mean end to end separation $\langle R^2 \rangle$ can be calculated. Once the value of $\langle R^2 \rangle$ is known the length of the long straight polymer chain (L) can be also calculated.

The eqs. (7) to (13) may be considered as a result of mathematical methods like second order partial differential equation, Taylor's expansion series and Laplace transformation within ranges or limits.

Again when the eqs. (11) to (13) are validated computationally for the biopolymers like Catalase, Myosin and Bushy shunt virus through an object oriented programming language like C++. The results obtained are as follows.

Enter data index : 03

Enter the value of radius of gyration (R_g) in nm :

3.98	46.8	12
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The value of $\langle R^2 \rangle$:

47.5212	6570.72	432.00
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The value of long straight polymer chain (L) in nm :

3.2468	38.1792	99.7895
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The above result is interpreted as follows. The mean end to end separation $\langle R^2 \rangle$ increases from Catalase, Bushy shunt virus to Myosin. The value of $\langle R^2 \rangle$ also supports the long straight length (L) for the above biopolymers considering cubic lattice by applying rotational isomeric model³ (RIM).

Experimental

The output eqs. (7) to (13) obtained by mathematical

analysis like Taylor's expansion series, second order partial differential equation and Laplace transformation are fitted with standard data¹⁰ to compute the value of mean square end to end separation $\langle R^2 \rangle$ and straight length (L) of a biopolymer chain like Catalase, Myosin and Bushy shunt virus. The data¹⁰ are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1 ¹⁰		
Biopolymer	Molecular weight (M) kg/mol	Radius of gyration (R_g) (nm)
Catalase	225	3.98
Bushy shunt virus	10600	12
Myosin	493	46.8

The standard data are executed by an object oriented programming language like C++ through the eqs. (11)

to (13) for which the schematic flow diagram is shown below.

Computational flow diagram scheme for Rotational Isomeric Model (RIM)

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